

OBTAINING CRYSTALS IN CLAY CERAMICS BASED ON PHOSPHOGYPSUM

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Abstract. *The purpose of the scientific work is to obtain ceramic mixtures using waste phosphogypsum and secondary kaolin, as the cheapest and most economically viable, by activating them with mineral additives, as well as to study the physicochemical, physico-chemical properties of the obtained ceramic masses.*

To achieve the goal, the following tasks are considered and solved: analysis of industrial waste used in the construction industry; development of preparation technology, selection of the optimal composition of phosphogypsum ceramic material with the addition of mineral additives; determination of the main physico-technical and physico-chemical characteristics of the obtained phosphogypsum ceramic.

The research developed environmentally friendly technologies for the processing of phosphogypsum - a large tonnage waste from the production of phosphorus fertilizers, overburden - secondary unenriched kaolin, and one of the ways to solve the environmental problem, which is based on the use of large-tonnage secondary raw materials, as well as man-made waste to obtain few energy-intensive building materials. The chemical and mineralogical composition and properties of phosphogypsum from the Almalyk chemical plant and secondary kaolin from the Angren deposit have been studied. The possibility of obtaining new compositions of ceramic materials for facing slabs using phosphogypsum and kaolin clay compositions in the presence of various additives has been studied.

Keywords: *phosphogypsum; industrial waste; The Match!; KAFEL-1 and KAFEL-2; reactions phases of carbon components; ceramic mass; phase of graphite.*

Introduction: There are various methods for dealing with waste, such as burial, placement in engineered landfills, incineration, and recycling into secondary raw materials. Recycling is considered the more promising method. When comparing landfilling and incineration, incineration causes less harm to the environment. On the other hand, incineration results in the loss of economic benefits from recycling. Despite the continuous development and implementation of new technologies for waste neutralization, utilization, and recycling, landfilling remains a widespread practice in most countries.

The article proposes the recycling of phosphogypsum, a chemical production waste, into secondary raw materials.

Result and discussion: In the experiment, two types of clay ceramics, designated as KAFEL-1 and KAFEL-2, were used. Both samples were obtained by melting solid phosphogypsum waste at high temperatures, which led to the formation of various crystalline phases. X-ray phase analysis (XRD) was used to analyze the resulting phases, along with the Match! software for the identification and quantitative assessment of crystalline compounds.

1. X-ray phase analysis (XRD) was conducted in the angular range of 2θ from 5.110° to 70.110° for the KAFEL-2 sample and from 4.700° to 69.700° for the KAFEL-1 sample. Data smoothing and background radiation correction were performed.

2. The Match! software was used to compare the experimental data with a database of crystalline structures, allowing the identification of the main phases and the calculation of their percentage content using the Reference Intensity Ratio (RIR) method.

The analysis of the KAFEL-1 and KAFEL-2 samples revealed significant differences in their crystalline structures. Let's examine the results for each of the samples.

****Material Composition of Kafel-1****

№	Secondary kaolin	Phosphogypsum	Angren gypsum	Quartz sand, pegmatite.
1	24	0	20	56
2	19	5	20	56
3	14	10	20	56
4	9	15	20	56

Analysis Results

Phase composition (Weight %)

Elemental composition (Weight %)

Index	Amount (%)	Name	Formula sum	Element	Amount (weight %)
A	2.8	Trirubidium Hydrogen bisulfate	H O8 Rb3 S2	C	97.2%(*)
B	97.2	Graphite	C	Rb	1.6%
	82.6	Unidentified peak area		O	0.8%(*)
				S	0.4%
				H	0.0%(*)
				*LE (sum)	98.0%

Amounts calculated by RIR (Reference Intensity Ratio) method

Table 1. Composition of Crystalline Phases in Sample KAFEL-1

Component	Formula	Content percentage (%)
Graphite	C	97.2
Trihydrogen rubidium bisulfate	Rb ₃ HO ₈ S ₂	2.8
Unidentified peaks	-	82.6

The main crystalline phase in sample KAFEL-1 is graphite (97.2%). This indicates that during the melting of phosphogypsum, carbonization occurs, which may be related to the reduction

reactions of carbon-containing components at high temperatures. The presence of trihydrogen rubidium bisulfate (2.8%) suggests a possible presence of phosphate compounds in the starting material. However, a large portion of the peaks (82.6%) remains unidentified, indicating the presence of additional phases or impurities that were not identified during the analysis.

Material Composition of Kafel-2

№	Feldspar	White kaolin	Gray kaolin	Red kaolin	Sand	Liquid glass	STPP	Phosphogypsum
1	30	10	10	10	15	20	5	0
2	30	10	10	5	15	20	5	5
3	30	5	10	5	15	20	5	10

The research data indicate that in the ceramic mass consisting of 60% clay and 10% phosphogypsum, solid-phase processes occur most intensively, resulting in sintered samples characterized by high density. The analysis of experimental data suggests that the sintering process at 1100 °C occurs in a solid state—with the involvement of a liquid phase that intensifies the sintering processes and solid-phase transformations.

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Table 2. Composition of crystalline phases in the sample KAFEL-2

Component	Formula	Content percentage (%)
Quartz	SiO ₂	18.6
Silicon oxide	SiO ₂	81.0
Tungsten	W	0.5
Unidentified peaks	-	27.1

Sample KAFEL-2 differs from KAFEL-1 in that its main phases are quartz (18.6%) and silicon oxide (81.0%). Both of these compounds are important components that determine the mechanical strength and thermal stability of the ceramics. The presence of tungsten (0.5%) indicates impurities of metallic compounds that may enhance the thermal stability and density of the material. However, 27.1% of the peaks remain unidentified, which requires further investigation.

The results of the phase analysis show that both types of ceramics contain crystalline phases that can influence their physicochemical properties.

1. In sample KAFEL-1, the predominant phase of graphite may significantly reduce the electrical conductivity of the material, which could be beneficial for applications in electrical insulation. The presence of phosphate compounds in small quantities may also confer fire resistance and increased resistance to chemical corrosion on the material.

2. In sample KAFEL-2, the content of silicon oxide and quartz indicates its suitability for construction materials where high mechanical strength and resistance to chemical exposure are important. Such materials can be used in the production of tiles, bricks, and other ceramic products.

Unidentified peaks in both samples require further analysis, as their identification could lead to the discovery of other valuable phases that may affect the material properties.

The building materials industry is a fundamental sector of the construction complex. It is one of the most material-intensive industries. Material intensity is determined by the ratio of the

quantity or cost of material resources used in production to the total volume of output. Considering that many mineral and organic wastes are chemically and technically similar to natural raw materials, and in many cases have several advantages (preliminary thermal treatment, increased dispersion, etc.), the use of industrial waste in the production of building materials is one of the main directions for reducing the material intensity of this mass, high-tonnage production. At the same time, reducing the volumes of extracted natural raw materials and waste disposal has significant economic and environmental importance. In some cases, the use of raw materials from industrial waste dumps almost completely meets the industry's needs for natural resources.

This study demonstrates the possibility of using phosphogypsum to create ceramic materials with diverse crystalline structures. The predominance of graphite phases in KAFEL-1 and silica phases in KAFEL-2 indicates a wide range of applications for such materials, from electrical insulation to the construction industry.

Further research should focus on optimizing the technological process and studying the influence of various additives on the phase composition of the ceramics, which will enhance the operational characteristics of the materials and expand their applications.

A vast number of methods for utilizing phosphogypsum have been proposed; however, despite this, the volumes of its disposal, compared to production, remain insignificant (according to data from the 1990s, the percentage of recycled phosphogypsum in our country was 17.4%). Many of the proposed solutions lead to secondary emissions into the atmosphere and hydrosphere and the formation of secondary waste that is even more hazardous than landfill waste [2; 18; 22].

The needs of the building materials industry for gypsum raw materials can almost entirely be met by gypsum-containing industrial waste, primarily phosphogypsum. A number of technologies for producing building and high-strength gypsum from phosphogypsum have been developed to date, but their implementation remains insufficient. This is partly due to the existing pricing policy for natural raw materials, which does not fully encourage the use of alternative secondary raw material resources. In Japan, where there are no indigenous deposits of natural gypsum, phosphogypsum is almost completely utilized for the production of various gypsum products.

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